

DUAL POLARIZED RCS GRAZING ANGLE CHARACTERISTICS OF INTERNAL GRAVITY WAVES

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ABSTRACT -- Grazing angle dependencies of radar cross section (RCS) are shown to differ for horizontally (HH) and vertically (VV) polarized X-band marine radar sea scatter from internal gravity wave (IGW) spatial modulations. For these internal gravity waves, observed off the coast of North Carolina, an IGW crest-to-trough modulation of 30-dB is observed at HH at 1° , but only 10 dB at VV. The HH RCS decreases with increasing grazing angle, roughly to the minus one power, whereas VV RCS increases as for the composite model, but only to the first power. The HH/VV RCS ratio is 10 dB at 1° , again opposite that expected from the two scale model, and decreases to -10 dB at 10° grazing. The two scale model with wave-current modulation of short waves by wave-current interaction predicts a decrease in modulation as grazing is approached, opposite the results presented here. We suggest an influence of wave breaking radar scatter sources to explain these internal wave results, similar to arguments made for breaking wave scatter occurring near fronts.

INTRODUCTION

Experiments were conducted to study the sources of anomalous radar scattering properties of submesoscale ocean surface features, such as fronts and internal gravity waves, under the sponsorship of the ONR/NRL High Resolution Advanced Research Initiative (High Res ARI). A number of principal investigations were involved with the ARI, ranging from insitu sensing of small scale wave spectra using laser scanning devices, wind stress measurements, overflights of real aperture radars, SAR and Interferometric SAR, HF radar mapping of ocean current fields, and acoustic sensing of the water environment. The work presented here was directed at understanding the scattering mechanisms that are responsible for imaging these submesoscale features at low grazing angles where HH scatter is not well described by conventional radar scattering models (Trizna & Carlson [1]; Trizna. [2]).

The polarization behavior of low grazing angle radar imagery from fronts have been hypothesized as due to different scattering mechanisms dominating for HH and VV [ibid.],

based upon azimuthal characteristics of the ambient sea scatter. The VV echo was shown to have an azimuthal dependence similar to higher grazing angle scatterometry, and could be fit by an empirical Wentz model algorithm, which agrees generally with the predictions of a two scale model. Alternatively, the lack of a strong echo downwind for HH forces the consideration of strongly asymmetric scattering sources, such as bores measured by Duncan [3] and calculated by Longuet-Higgins and Cleaver [4]. At intermediate angles, above 20° , bound capillary waves have been hypothesized as a source of anomalously high HH scatter at higher Doppler frequency shift than can be explained by orbital wave current modulation of short linear Bragg waves [5].

The HH and VV echo have also been shown to exhibit different behavior in the distribution function properties as a function of local grazing angle [1]. In this work we discuss grazing angle differences for the two polarizations for a series of calibrated marine radar images of internal gravity waves.

EXPERIMENT DESIGN

The radar data were collected using a dual polarized marine radar that could be switched from horizontal to vertical polarization on alternate antenna rotations. The characteristics of the radar were described in [1]. The received power signal was transformed for each radar pixel to normalized radar cross section (NRCS), σ^0 , by first solving the radar equation:

$$P_R = P_T G_T G_R \lambda^2 \sigma (4\pi)^3 R^{-4} \quad (1)$$

and then using radar cell area normalization to get, σ^0 :

$$\sigma^0 = \sigma / (R d\phi c dt) \quad (2)$$

where σ is the measured radar cross section, $d\phi$ is the transmit-receive antenna 3-dB beamwidth product, c is the speed of light, and dt is the radar pulse length. Data were collected every minute, switching polarization within 4 seconds for near simultaneous images for the two polarizations. Thus any polarization differences observed should be due to scattering mechanisms differences exclusively.

DUAL POLARIZED SEA SCATTER IMAGERY

Examples of HH and VV radar images after this transformation from P_R to σ^0 for each pixel are shown in Fig. 1, where the range-time data format has also been transformed to a Cartesian coordinate system. The noise floor submitted to Eq. 1 at long ranges raises it to the 1st power, thus giving the an apparent range dependent NRCS background floor. For the 25 MHz sampling rate used, the 256 samples corresponds to 1536 m of total range coverage. The examples in Fig. 1 of HH and VV imagery of internal waves suggest that composite scatter model may not properly describe the HH echo.

Figure 1. Marine radar images of internal gravity waves are shown for horizontal and vertical polarization, left to right, for two different azimuthal aspects relative to the wave direction, showing a much larger spatial modulation for HH than VV.

The IGW's are assumed to be propagation left to right, as evidenced by the strongest echo being associated with the first crest of the wave train, so that the upper image pair is illuminating the IGW's into the front edge of the wave train, while the lower pair illuminates them from behind. The wind direction analysis has not been completed as yet, however.

The data were further quantified by calculating a mean value over three range samples and 20° in azimuth, centered about the normal direction to the IGW crests. The grazing angle was determined by the height of the antenna and slant range to the center of three radar cells, and results of this calculation of area RCS means is shown in Figure 2. The raw data in radial coordinates were used to average, so the sample number across azimuth did not change with range.

Figure 2. Mean RCS vs grazing angle for HH (solid) and VV (open) figures shows larger HH crest to trough modulations, and larger HH RCS at low angles.

It is clear that the HH echo is larger than VV at the lowest grazing angles, as was observed for fronts [2], so that wave breaking processes may be dominating the HH echo here as well. A similar argument would explain the deep IGW crest-to-trough modulations, assuming that the trough RCS's are determined by the composite model under local wind forcing. The 20 dB VV/HH ratio in the IGW troughs is in agreement with the composite model here. Due to the strong directional dependence of bore features, there should be a difference in azimuthal aspect for the HH echo as was seen in [1], but this data separation with aspect has not been done yet.

IGW CREST-TRough DATA SUMMARY

Results of mean value analyses for 47 images were further analyzed by picking the HH and VV RCS values at the peaks and troughs of plots such as these, cataloguing the grazing angle for each, and providing a summary plot shown below in Fig. 3. No attempt was made to differentiate between the up and down wave look, but differences are expected to occur.

Crest and Trough RCS Values

The first plots show all crest RCS values (solid circles) and trough values (open circles) plotted versus grazing angle, for the HH data in the upper left, and for VV in the middle left. The HH crest maxima tend to increase with shallower grazing angles, while the trough minima are nearly constant with grazing angle. Neither of these results is consistent with a composite scattering model based on Bragg scatter.

The VV data in middle left show a different behavior, a weak decline with decreasing grazing angle, in the right sense as predicted by the composite model, but not quite as rapid as expected. The tough VV echo declines as grazing angle to the minus 2 power, which is weaker than predicted by the composite model, unless strong wave current interactions are steepening the intermediate waves more that expected in a wind driven free wave system.

Figure 3. Summary of IGW crest/trough results for many radar images, but mixing azimuthal results.

HH/VV Ratios

The mean RCS polarization ratio for the IGW crests and troughs are plotted in the lower left and right plots in Fig. 3, respectively. The crest ratio is never greater than -10 dB, suggesting feature scatter dominates the HH echo, assuming that VV is due to the composite model. In the case of the IGW troughs, at 10° the ratio is estimated to be -20 dB, in agreement with the composite model.

IGW Crest to Trough Ratios

The NRCS ratio of IGW crest to adjacent trough is plotted for each polarization, HH and VV, in the upper right and middle right plot of Fig. 3, respectively. These results are not sorted by azimuthal aspect (up-wave vs down-wave), so that the spread observed might be expected. A line has been drawn through the body of the HH data and intersects at the 25-dB level for 1° grazing angle, while for VV the corresponding value is 10 dB, both in general agreement with the data shown in Fig. 2. At 10° the HH data approach 5 dB, in general agreement with the values shown in the upper plots of Fig. 2, while the VV data show an apparent minimum near 7° before turning up. The number of VV points above 7° may not be statistically

significant, however, but further data will be reviewed to study this effect more carefully. It is noted that the Brewster angle for VV X-band sea scatter is between 5 and 7° .

SUMMARY

We have analyzed 47 image pairs for horizontally and vertically polarized X-band marine radar data, and found that the HH modulation from internal gravity wave currents is apparently being driven by small scale breaking by the current convergence zone at the IGW crests. The grazing angle dependence for HH sea scatter near the IGW crests increasing with shallower grazing angle, a trend opposite that expected from the composite scatter model. For VV scatter, the grazing angle dependence at the IGW crests has the same sense as the composite model predicts. The HH/VV NRCS ratio is greater than one near the crests, again counter to the predictions of the composite model. In the IGW troughs, the polarization ratio and general behavior is closer to that predicted by the two scale model. Experiments are planned in which the short wave characteristics will be measured to test the hypothesis of small scale breakers as dominant HH scatters.

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